

**COMPARING THE REPRESENTATION OF WOMEN IN RUSSIAN AND
ENGLISH LITERATURE**

**СРАВНЕНИЕ ПРЕДСТАВЛЕННОСТИ ЖЕНЩИНЫ В РУССКОЙ И
АНГЛИЙСКОЙ ЛИТЕРАТУРЕ**

**RUS VA INGLIZ ADABIYOTIDA AYOLLARNING SIYMOSINI
TAQQOSLASH**

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Abstract: The main aim of this article is to compare women's descriptions in English and Russian literature. The depth of their ideological content, their unwavering pursuit of important issues and their ability to address them, their compassion for humanity, and the reality of their portrayals of reality have always been the defining characteristics of both works of literature. Writers from both Russia and England attempted to highlight our people's greatest traits in female representations. We meet such lovely, chaste women in no other literature in the world; they stand out for having devoted, loving hearts and possessing a special spiritual beauty.

Keywords: English literature, Russian literature, female images, A.S Pushkin, Eugene Onegin, William Shakespeare, Desdemona, Othello

Аннотация: Основная цель данной статьи это сравнить описания женщин в английской и русской литературе. Глубина их идеологического содержания, их непоколебимое стремление к важным проблемам и их способность решать их, их сострадание к человечеству и реальность их изображения реальности всегда были определяющими характеристиками обоих литературных

произведений. Писатели как России, так и Англии пытались выделить главные черты нашего народа в женских образах. Таких милых, целомудренных женщин мы не встречаем ни в одной другой литературе мира; они отличаются преданным, любящим сердцем и особой духовной красотой.

Ключевые слова: Английская литература, Русская литература, женские образы, А.С. Пушкин, Евгений Онегин, Уилиам Шекспир, Дездемона, Отелло

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolaning asosiy maqsadi ingliz va rus adabiyotida ayollarning tavsiflarini solishtirishdir. Ularning g'oyaviy mazmunining teranligi, muhim masalalarga tinimsiz intilishi va ularni hal eta olishi, insoniylikka mehr-shafqati, voqelikni aks ettiruvchi voqelik har ikkala adabiyot asarini ham belgilab beruvchi xususiyat bo'lib kelgan. Rossiya va Angliya yozuvchilari ayollar timsolida xalqimizning eng buyuk fazilatlarini yoritishga harakat qilishdi. Biz dunyoning hech bir adabiyotida bunday yoqimli, pokiza ayollarni uchratamiz; ular fidoyi, mehribon qalblari va o'ziga xos ma'naviy go'zallikka egaligi bilan ajralib turadi.

Kalit so'zlar: Ingliz adabiyoti, rus adabiyoti, ayol obrazlari, A.S.Pushkin, Yevgeniy Onegin, Vilyam Shekspir, Dezdemon, Otello.

INTRODUCTION

Only Russian authors placed a high value on describing the inner life and the nuanced experiences of the female heart. Our literature has been filled with the idea of a Russian heroine who is ready to do great things, has a fiery heart, and is warm-hearted ever since the twelfth century. "Eugene Onegin" is a poetry novel. It is among the greatest pieces of the renowned Russian classic, even if it isn't the best. For the first time, Tatiana Larina, a Russian woman who sings with love and affection and is the embodiment of her own ideal, is presented by A.S. Pushkin. A real divorced woman who was sent to Siberia is thought to be the model for this heroine.

"The ideal representation of Eugene Onegin's protagonist"

Pushkin gives his heroine Tatiana, a straightforward and yet incredibly common name. Despite having a genuine, likable, and organic personality, he cannot be characterized as a simpleton. The extraordinary depth of the soul is mixed with the protagonist's sincerity. She was raised surrounded by books because she is an avid reader, and her mother's stories are a world apart from her own. Tatiana is not used to loving her parents and playing with other kids, just like all of her peers. In front of the students, she presents herself as a lonely girl cut off from society. This is Pushkin's ideal depiction of Eugene Onegin, the main character in his book. He feels one with nature and follows its laws and rhythms because he loves it. For a girl, the opinions of the public do not really matter. He does, however, inhabit an idealistic, pure, and deeply spiritual world. He loves and cherishes himself, the country life, and being near nature. After getting married and leading a secular life in St. Petersburg, he eventually forgets about the life he had in his cherished village. Pushkin gives two detailed accounts of the novel's central characters.

Eugene Onegin and Tatiana Larina are attracted to each other while also resisting each other. A young man who has seen so much in the girl's life and still has hope for the future is touched by the pure and sincere heart of the girl. It's obvious throughout the book how empty Onegin's mind is and how fragile Larina's spirit is. Love has the power to transform everything, and Tatiana's love has grown to be powerful and genuine. However, Eugene Onegin completely loses it and won't acknowledge it. Passion or love? Tatiana was a wonderful girl who fell in love with her own fantasy rather than a real man. But the young man who was drawn to her because of her attractiveness and enigmatic side wasn't a romantic hero based on her own quirks, goals, and dreams. With the worldly life of man, he was corrupt, empty, and hopeless.

Nevertheless, Tatiana was not duped because he possessed the nobility of the nobility within him. After Eugene Onegin departed, the girl became extremely

aggressive. He was given the chance to transform and rediscover his previous spirit. However, he found it extremely challenging and incomprehensible, and as his detractors would sometimes refer to him, the "young old man" or "young man," he just chose to retire and carry on with his regular life. Eugene Onegin and Tatiana Larina will later get together in St. Petersburg. Then Onegin, not anyone else, is consumed by the flame of passion. Tatiana, on the other hand, has advanced in status and is no longer capable of loving her. On this occasion, though, he declines Eugenia—not out of retaliation or adherence to conventional wisdom. No matter what, he doesn't love her; he loves her. Still, she lives her life according to her irrational moral and spiritual beliefs, and she won't betray her rewarded husband. At the same time, he understands that Onegin is moved by passion and self-centered pride rather than genuine love.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

V.G. Belinskiy about Tatiana

The novel "Eugene Onegin" is a true encyclopedia of Russian life, and VG Belinsky provides a detailed description of the idealized version of the protagonist, describing the reality of the Russian woman. She sees Tatiana as a strong, deep woman who, despite the contradictions of complex spirits, occasionally lacks self-awareness. It is total, alone, and unadulterated. And it doesn't matter anymore if she's a socialite or just a regular village girl. His high spiritual integrity never leaves him, and the moral principles and values that reside within him always serve as his compass. Tatiana, his sister Olga, and the idealized protagonist of "Eugene Onegin" stand in sharp contrast to each other. The other is a naive, narrow-minded girl who is windy. Her hatred is made clear for the young man who fell deeply in love with her, Lensky, who calls Onegin into a duel and loses his life there as a result of his carelessness.

Tatiana and Olga require the depth and substance of other people's thoughts and deeds, which she is unable to provide, so she is unable to have a spiritual friendship with her irrational sister. Tatiana, in my opinion, is a beautiful person who appreciates harmony, beauty, and the natural world. He enjoys wandering through fields and deserts, thinking about the Moon, waiting for the sun to set, and taking in the stunning views of the natural world—especially in the winter. He even likes taking cold water baths. His concept is similar to that of the Pagans, in whom individuals are one with the natural world and the outside world without severing themselves, and in which they discover the answers to all of their inquiries. Tatiana is a believer in superstition, racism, dreams, and prophecy. And the relationship with nature is strengthened even more by this belief.

The representation of women in Shakespeare's plays

Women were not permitted on stages during Shakespeare's active years, as is widely known. Her well-known female roles, like Desdemona and Julietta, were all originally portrayed by men. Women are crucial to moving the plot along in many of William Shakespeare's dramas. Particularly in Shakespeare's tragedies, these women serve as the impetus for a drama in which other people's responses to situations that influence women's behavior unfold. In their esteemed roles, Macbeth in Macbeth and Desdemona in Othello both play this part. Notwithstanding the stark differences in their characters, both women play similar roles. Desdemona almost becomes a stereotypical woman after her marriage to Othello. Shakespeare plays with gender roles and significant plot devices in Desdemona and Mrs. Macbeth. Then, her depictions of women turn into nuanced critiques of the customs and attitudes toward women of Elizabethan society. It was crucial to make the shift from the Middle Ages to Elizabeth's reign. Shakespeare's day was a great one for women, as Judith Cook noted. Their influence could still be seen today, as the Tudors and the first women of Jacob in England were envious of their position.

RESULTS

In general, they are in better shape in the sixteenth century, Sharp. Women were welcomed with greater acclaim for some action during Queen Elizabeth's reign in the capital.

The ascent to power of Mary and Elizabeth I offered a strong, self-assured illustration of female dominance. Noble women flourished during the Renaissance, a period of strong England and occasionally strong women holding an iron grip on the throne. Socially acceptable actions—such as attending performances—were outlawed in early works.

Elizabeth I was a fervent theater enthusiast, so going to the theater has long been considered socially acceptable. According to literary scholar Wright, "Women visited the theater, and although they still could not attend any performances, they often found themselves in theatrical ruthless jokes about housewives." Shakespeare was conscious of these social shifts and drew inspiration for his plays from women in those evolving times. Wright states that Shakespeare would not be well-known for presenting the idea of a free, amazing woman if he had not been a highly knowledgeable and intelligent writer. Some produced females who were nearly as powerful and independent as males.

CONCLUSION

Shakespeare's portrayal of women in his plays reveals his views on women and their place in society. Shakespeare's plays frequently feature discrimination against women. Despite their obviously constrained social roles, Bard has demonstrated how they can impact the eras in which women live. Her poems highlight the disparity in perceptions that existed at the time between women from the upper and lower classes. It is said that born women are like "property" that is passed down from fathers to husbands. They are frequently socially restricted and unable to independently

investigate their surroundings. The majority of these women have experienced male control and coercion throughout their lives. Since women from lower social classes were seen as less significant than those from higher social classes, they were granted greater freedom of movement.

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